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Research on the processing technology of filter tea and instant granule tea from *Pleurotus citrinopileatus* Singer (1943) mushroom. Part I

**Nguyen Vu Thu Phuong^{1,*}, Vu Thi Van Phuong¹, Vu Hong Nhung¹,
Nguyen Thi Huong²**

¹ VietRAP Center for Scientific Research and Development, VietRap Trading Investment Joint Stock Company, 238 - Hoang Quoc Viet, Nghia Do, Hanoi, Vietnam

² High Technology Innovation Center, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology, 18 - Hoang Quoc Viet, Nghia Do, Hanoi, Vietnam

*E-mail address: phuongnvt.vietrap@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Tamogi mushroom (*Pleurotus citrinopileatus*), a culinary medicinal mushroom rich in β -glucans and antioxidant compounds, represents a promising raw material for functional beverage development. This study aimed to establish and optimize integrated processing technologies for two value-added products: filter tea and instant granule tea derived from Tamogi mushroom. Fresh Tamogi samples were subjected to cleaning, drying, grinding, aqueous extraction, concentration, formulation optimization, and granulation. The effects of key processing parameters, including drying conditions, extraction temperature, and formulation ratios, were systematically evaluated in relation to product quality, solubility, and sensory attributes. Results indicated that circulating air drying at 50-55 °C effectively preserved color and characteristic aroma while achieving adequate dehydration, whereas extraction at 90-100 °C maximized the recovery of bioactive compounds. Formulation optimization incorporating complementary mushrooms and natural flavor modifiers significantly improved sensory acceptability and functional performance. The optimized filter tea formulation (9.0:3.0:3.6:1.0:2.0:1.4) exhibited high infusion quality and balanced taste, while the optimized instant granule tea (7.0:3.0:2.0:1.0:6.0), combined with maltodextrin (0.05:1), demonstrated superior solubility, rapid dispersion, and minimal sediment formation. Overall, the developed processes provide a practical and scalable approach for producing Tamogi-based functional beverages, with instant granule tea showing greater potential for commercialization due to its enhanced convenience and physicochemical performance.

Keywords: Tamogi mushroom, *Pleurotus citrinopileatus*, drying, formulation, filter tea, instant tea

1. INTRODUCTION

Common edible species provide high-quality protein (including essential amino acids), dietary fiber (notably β -glucans), vitamins (B-complex, vitamin D after UV exposure), minerals (K, P, Se, Fe), and low fat and low calories. These features support balanced nutrition and micronutrient sufficiency, especially in plant-forward diets (Rathore, H. et al. 2017). Culinary-medicinal mushrooms are edible species that combine nutritional value with documented bioactive properties, making them relevant to public health, preventive medicine, and sustainable food systems (Chang, S. T. et al. 2017). Functional foods derived from medicinal mushrooms have attracted global interest due to their health-promoting properties (Wasser, S. P. (2014). Mushrooms' bioactive compounds, such as polysaccharides, triterpenoids, and phenolics, underpin multiple physiological benefits, including immune modulation, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, immune support during therapy, and metabolic health support (Zhang, M. et al. 2007).

Species like *Trametes versicolor* and *Ganoderma lucidum* contain β -glucans that enhance innate and adaptive immune responses. *T. versicolor* and *C. militaris* are studied as complementary agents (e.g., immune support during therapy) (Heleno, S. A. et al. 2015). Among them, *P. citrinopileatus* (Tamogi mushroom) is recognized as a valuable edible fungus rich in β -glucan, polysaccharides, ergothioneine, and essential amino acids (Siwulski, M. et al. 2017; Rodrigues, D.M.F.C. et al. 2015; Lin, S.Y. et al. 2016). Scientific studies have established the role of bioactive compounds in *P. citrinopileatus* in antioxidant activity, immune modulation, antihyperglycemic effect, and the prevention of chronic conditions (Lee, Y.L. et al. 2007; Yıldız, S. et al. 2017; Hu, S. et al. 2006; Hu, S. et al. 2005). Medicinal mushroom β -glucan plays an important role in various biological activities (Muthuraman KR et al. 2026).

P. citrinopileatus is grown in tropical or subtropical areas and mainly in China, India, Japan, and Korea. Locally available agricultural wastes such as sugar cane pomace, sawdust, rice straw, and coconut fiber waste are used for the cultivation of the mushrooms (Ahmed, S. A. et al. 2009; Liang, Z. et al. 2005; Singh, M.B. et al. 2011; Magdziak Z. et al. 2021). In Vietnam, Tamogi mushroom cultivation has developed owing to increasing market demand. However, its utilization remains largely limited to fresh consumption, resulting in low added value and short shelf life.

Several preparation technologies have been developed to formulate mushrooms into consumable products (Sknepnek A. et al. 2022; Dong Y. W. et al. 2021). Mushrooms are used to produce various kinds of beverages that satisfy consumers' needs for improving the quality of life due to their good nutrition, sensory pleasure, and beneficial effects on human health (Pavlović M. O. et al. 2023; Wu P. et al. 2022).

Processing *P. citrinopileatus* mushrooms into functional beverages such as filter tea (tea bags) and instant granule tea offers several advantages, including improved shelf stability, enhanced bioavailability of active compounds, and convenient consumption as functional foods (Yang JY. et al. 2025; Vamanu E. et al. 2021). Previous studies have demonstrated that extraction conditions, drying temperature, and formulation significantly influence the extraction of β -glucan (Thi, T.T. et al. 2023; Dung et al. 2026; Yen MT. et al. 2018).

However, systematic studies on the integrated processing of the *P. citrinopileatus* mushroom into tea products are still limited. Therefore, this study aims to develop processing technologies for filter tea and instant granule tea, optimize key technological parameters, and evaluate product quality, thus, the potential for commercialization and product development of Vietnam's National Program "One Commune One Product" for Rural Economic Development (OCOP).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Materials and equipment

Fresh Tamogi mushrooms were obtained from VietRap Co.'s GACP-WHO-compliant cultivation research model in Luong Son commune, Vietnam. Dried herbal additives, including *Cordyceps*, *T. versicolor*, *A. blazei* mushrooms, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, jujube fruit, and brown rice were supplied by VietRap Co. (Vietnam). Food-grade maltodextrin with solubility $\geq 100\text{g}/100\text{ ml}$ at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as a carrier agent was purchased from Zibo Qianhui Biological Technology Co. (China), and isomalt as a sweetener $> 98.0\%$ was purchased from Foodchem International Corporation (China). Ethanol 96% was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USS), and distilled water was produced by a laboratory Water Distiller, model WDST-S5 (China) on-site. A small grinder, model Sqm-2L from Changsha Samy Instruments & Equipment Co. (China), a small Granule Packing Machine, model DXDB-K80C from Ruian Sanyang Technology Co. (China), and a compact dry powder granulator, model Gk-100 M, from Gainjoys Technology Shenyang Co. (China) were used.

2. 2. Sample Preparation

Fresh mushrooms were cleaned, washed, and drained, then sliced into uniform pieces. Sliced mushrooms were dried under a temperature range of $70\text{-}80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an electric dryer to reduce the final moisture below 5% (Yen MT. et al. 2018). All the other dried herbal materials were sliced into uniform pieces and dried again under a temperature range of $70\text{-}80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to reduce the final moisture below 5%.

Preparation of extracts and powders from raw materials: The preparation of powders and extracts from *P. citrinopileatus*, *C. militaris*, *T. versicolor*, *G. glabra*, and brown rice was carried out following standardized procedures to ensure preservation of bioactive compounds and suitability for filter and instant tea applications. Fresh Tamogi mushrooms were washed thoroughly, drained, and sliced into uniform pieces (3-5 mm thickness). Dried raw materials (*Cordyceps*, *T. versicolor*, licorice, and brown rice) were cleaned to remove impurities and foreign matter. All materials were pre-treated to ensure uniform moisture content prior to drying. All materials were dried to reduce moisture content below 5-8% by circulating air drying ($50\text{-}55\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to ensure stability and facilitate grinding. Dried materials were ground using a laboratory grinder and sieved to obtain a uniform particle size of <80 mesh for filter tea and 80-120 mesh for instant tea.

The powders were stored in airtight containers at ambient temperature until further use. Aqueous extraction was performed to obtain bioactive compounds, particularly polysaccharides. Powdered samples were mixed with distilled water at a ratio of 1:10-1:20 (w/v). Extraction was carried out at $90\text{-}100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1-3 h. The mixture was filtered through muslin cloth or filter paper. The filtrate was collected as a crude extract. The obtained extracts

were concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator at 50-60 °C until the desired solid content (20-30%) was reached. This step minimized thermal degradation while increasing extract stability. The concentrated extracts were converted into powders using hot-air drying at 50-60 °C until the moisture was $\leq 8\%$. This process was applied to all mushroom materials and licorice. Brown rice was roasted prior to grinding to enhance flavor at a temperature of 120-150 °C, 15-25 min with continuous stirring. After roasting, the rice was cooled, ground, and sieved to obtain fine powder suitable for extraction. Aqueous extraction was carried out at 90 °C, subsequently concentrated and converted into powders by freeze drying.

2. 3. Processing of Filter Tea

The following steps were established to produce the Tamogi mushroom's filter tea (Jha DK. et al. 2020). Previously sliced and dried Tamogi mushroom pieces, *Cordyceps*, *T. versicolor*, *A. blazei* mushroom powder, jujube fruit powder, and *G. glabra* were coarse ground below 80 mesh. All the powders were mixed. Finally, they were packaged into tea bags at 2.0g per bag.

2. 4. Processing of Instant Granule Tea

The following steps were established to produce instant granule tea from the Tamogi mushroom (Sinija V.R. et al. 2007). Roasting of brown rice was carried out traditionally at 120-150 °C for 15-25 minutes, with continuous stirring to ensure uniform heating and prevent burning. All the materials, including Tamogi mushroom pieces, *Cordyceps* mushroom, *T. versicolor*, *G. glabra*, and roasted brown rice, were coarse ground below 80 mesh. All the powders were mixed and finally mixed with maltodextrin. The resulting powder mixture is granulated into small particles with a granule size of 1 mm at a drying temperature of 50-60 °C to reach a final moisture below 5%.

2. 5. Assessment of Organoleptic Parameters

Sensory evaluation of the tea beverages was carried out for color, aroma and taste (Shamim N. et al. 2020). The nature of the herbal ingredients in the tea bag formulation indicates its tea-dissolved color, while its taste and flavor are susceptible indicators. The tea-dissolved color was observed with the naked eye in white tube light. Its flavor was smelled for the flavor test. Its taste was tested on the taste buds of the tongue.

Test for Tamogi mushroom filter tea:

Each filter tea bag (2.0 g) was used for the test. Distilled water was heated to 95 ± 2 °C. One tea bag was immersed in 200 mL of hot distilled water and brewed for 3, 5, and 7 min without squeezing. After brewing, the tea bag was removed and allowed to drain for 30 s. Three parameters are evaluated by a panel of five tea experts. Infusion appearance should be clear to slightly turbid; color is scored visually; and sensory attributes with characteristic mushroom-herbal aroma, mild umami, and slightly sweet tastes, and no bitterness aftertaste are acceptable.

Test for instant Tamogi mushroom tea:

A 3.0 g portion of instant tea granules was accurately weighed and added to 150 mL of hot water at 80-90 °C. The sample was stirred manually for 30 s. Dissolution was observed immediately and after standing for 5 min. Several parameters are evaluated by a panel of five

tea experts: dissolution time required for complete dissolution; visual appearance for dispersibility during stirring, turbidity, and sediment; mouthfeel characteristics for smoothness and grittiness; and sensory score for taste, aroma, sweetness, and aftertaste.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Effect of Tamogi mushroom drying methods and conditions

The effects of different drying methods and conditions on moisture content and sensory quality for fresh Tamogi mushrooms were systematically evaluated. Under experiment 1, for a 9 h drying time, hot-air drying at 45 °C resulted in a relatively high residual moisture content (18%) of Tamogi mushrooms, indicating insufficient dehydration. Increasing the temperature to 50-55 °C significantly reduced moisture to 10-11%, while further increasing to 60-65 °C achieved 8% moisture. However, higher temperatures adversely affected sensory attributes, leading to a transition in Tamogi mushroom color from bright yellow to light brown and noticeable odor changes.

This suggests that although higher temperatures improve drying efficiency, they may promote thermal degradation of Tamogi mushrooms, negatively impacting product quality (Adamska, I. et al. 2025). In comparison, circulating air drying at 50-55 °C achieved a desirable balance, reducing moisture to 8-10% while maintaining the Tamogi mushrooms' bright yellow color and characteristic odor. Similarly, freeze drying at room temperature conditions resulted in a moisture content below 8% and preserved both Tamogi mushroom color and odor, indicating superior retention of quality attributes. These findings confirm that non-thermal or mild drying approaches are more effective in preserving sensory characteristics. Under experiment 2 with an extended drying time of 18 h for Tamogi mushrooms, the moisture content further decreased across all conditions. At 45 °C, the moisture of the Tamogi mushroom was reduced to 11%, while temperatures of 50-55 °C and 60-65 °C achieved levels below 8%. However, prolonged exposure at elevated temperatures intensified quality deterioration, with samples at 60-65 °C exhibiting Tamogi mushroom dark brown coloration and pronounced odor changes. In contrast, circulating air drying maintained stable sensory properties even with extended drying durations, achieving moisture levels of 10%, 8%, and 7% at increasing time intervals (18, 36-40, and 48-60 h, respectively). Overall, the results demonstrate a clear trade-off between drying efficiency and product quality for fresh Tamogi mushrooms.

Table 1. Effect of drying methods and conditions for fresh Tamogi mushrooms.

Condition/Method		Hot air oven			Circulating air	Freeze dry
Exp	Temperature, °C	45	50-55	60-65	50-55	T room
1	Drying time, h	9	9	9	9	9
	Moisture, %	18	10-11	8	8-10	<8
	Sensory: color	Bright yellow	Light brown	Light brown	Bright yellow	Bright yellow
	Sensory: odor	Characteristic	Slight change	Odor change	Characteristic	Characteristic

Condition/Method		Hot air oven			Circulating air	Freeze dry
2	Drying time, h	18	18	18	18/36-40/48-60	No experiment
	Moisture, %	11	<8	<8	10/ 8/ 7	
	Sensory: color	Bright yellow	Light brown	Dark brown	Bright yellow	
	Sensory: odor	Characteristic	Odor change	Odor change	Characteristic	

While higher temperatures and longer drying times effectively reduce moisture content, they significantly compromise sensory attributes. Freeze drying provided the best quality retention but may be limited by higher operational costs, making it more suitable for high-value applications. Among the evaluated methods, circulating air drying at 50-55 °C represents the most suitable condition, achieving adequate dehydration while preserving color and characteristic aroma.

3. 2. Formulation and quality of filter tea

Starting with *P. citrinopileatus* as the primary ingredient, the rationale of the inclusion of additional mushroom and plant components in the new Tamogi-based filter tea formulation is justified by their functional synergy, sensory balancing, and infusion performance, all critical for a filter tea. *P. citrinopileatus* is the core component of the new Tamogi filter tea. It provides β -glucans and polysaccharides for immune-modulating potential, a mild umami profile for a natural savory base, and good hot-water infusion. However, Tamogi alone often yields a noticeable earthy and mushroom odor, a limited flavor complexity, and a moderate solubility of actives within a short brew time. Therefore, complementary ingredients are added to enhance both functionality and drinkability. Some mushrooms available in Vietnam are being studied to be formulated in synergy with the core Tamogi mushroom to enhance the bioactivity of the new formulation. *C. militaris*, a popular mushroom in Vietnam, is considered a first complementary ingredient. It provides cordycepin and nucleosides, enhances energy metabolism and immune support, and adds light umami without excessive bitterness (Jędrejko KJ. et al. 2021).

Secondly, *T. versicolor* mushroom is selected as it is rich in PSK/PSP polysaccharides with strong antioxidant and immunomodulatory effects (Habtemariam S. 2020). Its addition complements Tamogi β -glucans, leading to broader immune profile. A third mushroom ingredient added is *A. blazei* with high β -glucan content. In the new formulation, it contributes to metabolic and anti-inflammatory support and adds subtle nutty notes, improving flavor depth (Angeli JP. et al. 2009). Together, these mushrooms create a multi-component functional system, enhancing immune modulation, antioxidant activity, and nutritional diversity. Sensory balancing of new tea formulation is critical for consumer acceptance. Our choice is *Z. jujube* with natural sweetness and fruity aroma. It masks earthy/mushroom notes, improves color (golden infusion), and is traditionally associated with digestive and calming effects (Abdoul-Azize S. 2016; Liu R. et al. 2024). The other ingredient chosen is *G. glabra* as it provides lasting sweetness (glycyrrhizin), acts as a flavor harmonizer, reduces bitterness and enhances aftertaste, and improves mouthfeel (smoothness) (Lim TK. 2015; El-Lahot, M.S. et al. 2017).

These two added ingredients are essential because mushroom-only teas are often not palatable. They convert new formulations into a consumer-friendly functional beverage. Five formulations were designed using a mixture optimization approach to balance solubility and sensory attributes as above reasoned and presented in Table 2. Progressive adjustment of mushroom ratios, including Tamogi, Cordyceps, *T. versicolor*, and *A. blazei* mushrooms, and other flavor modifiers, including jujube fruit and *G. glabra* led to the final optimized formulation.

The initial formulation (F1), characterized by a higher proportion of all the mushroom powders, exhibited a strong earthy flavor and slight bitterness, which negatively affected sensory acceptance despite moderate solubility. Gradual adjustment of the formulation in F2 reduced bitterness but did not fully eliminate the dominant Tamogi mushroom taste. Further optimization in F3 improved both solubility and sensory balance, indicating the beneficial effect of increasing jujube content as a natural flavor modulator. In F4, although sweetness was enhanced by increasing *G. glabra*, the characteristic Tamogi mushroom profile became less pronounced. The final optimized formulation (F5), with a ratio of 9.0/ 3.0/ 3.6/ 1.0/ 2.0/ 1.4, achieved the best overall performance. This formulation demonstrated very high solubility, rapid dispersion in hot water, and a well-balanced sensory profile, combining mild umami, pleasant sweetness, and absence of bitterness. The synergistic interaction between mushroom components and flavor-enhancing agents (jujube and licorice) was identified as the key factor contributing to improved palatability.

Table 2. Formulation screening leading to the optimized Tamogi-based blend.

Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Tamogi	10.0	9.5	9.0	8.8	9.0
Cordyceps	4.0	3.5	3.2	3.0	3.0
<i>T. versicolor</i>	4.0	3.8	3.7	3.5	3.6
<i>A. blazei</i>	1.5	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0
Jujube	1.5	1.8	2.0	2.2	2.0
Licorice	1.0	1.2	1.1	1.5	1.4
Solubility	Moderate	Moderate to high	High	High	Very high
Sensory attributes	Strong mushroom, slight bitterness	Less bitter, earthy	Balanced, mild umami	Slightly sweet, weaker mushroom note	Balanced, pleasant sweetness, no bitterness
Overall assessment	Acceptable	Acceptable	Good	Good	Excellent

The results confirm that fine-tuning the ratio between all the functional mushroom powders and natural flavor modifiers is essential to achieve both functional efficacy and consumer acceptability. The optimized formulation provides a strong basis for further product

development, including instant tea, nutraceutical powders, or functional beverages. The tea from Tamogi and other ingredients has a light yellow-brown color, a characteristic mushroom flavor, and a mild, slightly sweet taste. The combination of Tamogi mushroom with Cordyceps, *T. versicolor*, *A. blazei*, jujube, and licorice enables a synergistic formulation that enhances bioactivity, sensory quality, and infusion efficiency, making it highly suitable for development as a functional filter tea product.

3. 4. Formulation and quality of instant granule tea

The formulation of instant granule tea based on Tamogi mushroom required the integration of functional mushrooms, natural flavor modifiers, and technological carriers. Starting with *P. citrinopileatus* as the primary ingredient, the formulation of an instant granule tea requires not only functional efficacy but also rapid solubility, dispersibility, and acceptable sensory properties. As the core ingredient, Tamogi mushroom powder provides polysaccharides (β -glucans) for immune-supporting activity, mild umami taste as a base flavor for a functional beverage, and water-extractable compounds suitable for instant tea. However, Tamogi alone has limited solubility in granular form, exhibits an earthy odor and flat taste profile, and requires carriers and flavor modifiers for instant applications. Therefore, additional ingredients are formulated to enhance functionality. Two mushrooms are being studied to be formulated in synergy with the core Tamogi mushroom to enhance the bioactivity of the new formulation. Cordyceps mushroom, compatible with hot-water extraction, can enhance bioactivity (cordycepin, nucleosides), and improve functional value (energy, immunity) (Jędrejko KJ. et al. 2021).

T. versicolor mushroom provides PSP/PSK polysaccharides, strengthens antioxidant and immune effects, and complements Tamogi in functional synergy (Habtemariam S.2020). Sensory attributes of the new instant tea formulation are critical for consumer acceptance. Our first choice is Licorice, acting as a natural sweetener (glycyrrhizin), masking bitterness and enhancing aftertaste, and improving mouthfeel and smoothness (Lim TK. 2015; El-Lahot, M.S. et al. 2017). Secondly, brown rice as a carrier and bulking agent can enhance granulation and flowability, provide roasted aroma and mild sweetness, and improve instant dispersion behavior (Wongsa J. et al. 2025; He M. et al. 2024). Together, these ingredients create a balanced system with bioactive mushrooms functionality, licorice and brown rice sensory adjustment, and easier granulation-friendly matrix technological processing.

Five formulations, designed as above reasoned and evaluated for solubility, dispersibility, and sensory attributes, were presented in Table 3. The optimal weight ratio was determined as Tamogi mushrooms powder/ *Cordyceps* mushroom powder/ *T. versicolor* powder/ *G. glabra* powder/ brown rice powder at 37.0%/ 16.0%/ 10.0%/ 5.0%/ 32.0%. To improve instant properties, the optimized powder blend was mixed with maltodextrin as a carrier. The optimized ratio of tea materials/ maltodextrin was 0.05/ 1. In the formulation, the maltodextrin enhances solubility and dispersibility, prevents agglomeration, and improves granule stability.

The new Tamogi mushroom-based instant tea formulations showed the dissolution time ≤ 30 -60 s; uniform dispersion and no clumping appearance; no sediment; smooth and non-gritty mouthfeel characteristics; and balanced taste, mild umami aroma, and pleasant sweetness. The optimized ratio of Tamogi, Cordyceps, *T. versicolor*, licorice, and brown rice (7.0:3.0:2.0:1.0:6.0) provided the best balance between solubility, dispersibility, and sensory quality. Instant tea showed better performance due to the extraction and concentration steps. The incorporation of maltodextrin at a ratio of 0.05:1 significantly improved the instant

properties of the formulation. The resulting granules, with a particle size of approximately 1 mm, exhibited rapid dissolution, minimal sediment formation, and high consumer acceptability, making the formulation suitable for industrial production of functional instant mushroom tea.

Table 3. Formulation screening leading to the optimized Tamogi-based instant granule tea.

Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Tamogi	8.0	7.5	7.2	6.8	7.0
Cordyceps	3.5	3.2	3.0	2.8	3.0
<i>T. versicolor</i>	2.5	2.3	2.1	2.0	2.0
Licorice	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.2	1.0
Brown rice	5.2	6.1	6.7	7.2	6.0
Solubility	Moderate	Moderate-high	High	High	Very high
Dispersibility	Slight clumping	Improved	Good	Good	Excellent
Sensory	Strong earthy taste	Balanced but mild	Improved flavor	Slightly diluted	Balanced, mild umami, pleasant sweetness
Overall	Acceptable	Good	Good	Good	Excellent

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study successfully established integrated processing technologies for the development of filter tea and instant granule tea from *Pleurotus citrinopileatus*, providing a scientific basis for value-added utilization of this functional mushroom. The results demonstrated that drying conditions significantly influenced product quality, with circulating air drying at 50-55 °C offering an optimal balance between dehydration efficiency and preservation of sensory attributes. Although freeze drying yielded superior quality retention, its higher operational cost limits its applicability for large-scale production.

Formulation optimization revealed that the incorporation of complementary medicinal mushrooms and natural flavor modifiers is essential to achieve both functional efficacy and consumer acceptability. For filter tea, the optimized formulation (9.0:3.0:3.6:1.0:2.0:1.4) exhibited high solubility and a well-balanced sensory profile, characterized by mild umami taste, pleasant sweetness, and absence of bitterness. For instant granule tea, the optimized ratio (7.0:3.0:2.0:1.0:6.0), combined with maltodextrin as a carrier (0.05:1), significantly improved solubility, dispersibility, and granule stability, resulting in rapid dissolution, minimal sediment, and high consumer acceptability. Both products demonstrated favorable sensory quality and notable antioxidant activity, highlighting their potential as functional beverages. Compared to filter tea, instant granule tea showed superior performance in terms of solubility and convenience, indicating greater potential for commercialization. The results provide a foundation for industrial production and commercialization of Tamogi-based functional

beverages. Despite these promising results, the study is limited by the lack of clinical validation of health benefits and long-term stability evaluation under different storage conditions. Future research should focus on the standardization of bioactive compounds (e.g., β -glucans), in vivo and clinical studies, and pilot-scale production optimization to facilitate industrial application. Overall, the developed processing technologies are simple, cost-effective, and scalable, providing a practical pathway for the industrial production and commercialization of Tamogi-based functional tea products, thereby contributing to the diversification of mushroom-derived nutraceuticals and the development of rural bioeconomy value chains.

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